

D7.1 CDUE-Plan

Communication, Dissemination, Upscaling and Exploitation Plan of the Europe-LAND project

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

CDUE	Communication, dissemination, upscaling, exploitation
CoP	(online) Community of Practice
HAW (Hamburg)	University of Applied Sciences Hamburg
KPI	Key performance indicator
WP	Work package

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Executive Summary

This Communication, Dissemination, Upscaling and Exploitation (CDUE) Plan (together with its regular updates) pertains to deliverables D7.1 (and subsequent yearly updates D7.2, D7.3, D7.4) in Task 7.1 within the WP 7 Information, Communication, Upscaling, and Capacity-Building of the Europe-LAND project under Grant Agreement No. 101081307.

It is intended to provide a detailed strategy for CDUE activities for the whole project duration to enable the project to reach its intended reach and impact. As a living document with yearly updates, it will be continuously adapted and improved to accommodate changing communication needs and opportunities. Besides the intended communication activities, the document also details a monitoring and evaluation framework set-up for CDUE activities and to measure and quantify project impact.

Is initial version of the CDUE-Plan is due to be delivered in August 2023 (M3) and will be updated three times in the course of the project in months 15 (D7.2), 27 (D7.3) and 39 (D7.4).

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1. Introduction

Within the Europe-LAND project, work package 7 aims to generate visibility and awareness of the project and its activities as well as to engage and empower project stakeholders to build upon the outcomes on the longer term. WP7 will undertake a set of information, communication, upscaling and outreach activities, as well as capacity building programmes dedicated to land-use and land management in Europe to achieve these goals. In order to ensure maximum effectiveness and reach of the proposed activities, a detailed plan is needed. This deliverable D7.1 CDUE-Plan and its subsequent yearly updates explain in detail the strategy behind the communication, dissemination, upscaling and exploitation activities of the project.

As described in D1.1, section 3.3, the project differentiates between the terms “communication”, “dissemination”, and “exploitation”. For working definitions of the terms, please refer to D1.1. Communication focuses on informing about the project, whilst dissemination focuses on sharing project results. Exploitation aims at making use of project results through upscaling and replication of outcomes across Europe and beyond. All three forms of activities are relevant to the Europe-LAND project.

This deliverable explains in detail internal and external communication of the project. The most relevant stakeholders for the project were identified as well as their preferred communication channels. Based on this, a variety of communication activities will be utilized to reach the relevant stakeholders. These activities as well as the chosen approach are laid out in this document. A strategy for online communication via a project website and social media is also explained. As exploitation and upscaling of project results is of special interest to the Europe-LAND project, one section of this deliverable details how the proposed activities will aid the implementation of project results by stakeholders. As all partners of the project consortium will be actively involved in communication and dissemination activities, the document also outlines responsibilities of partners when communicating externally. Lastly, the document lays out a plan for the continuous monitoring and evaluation of communication and dissemination activities to ensure the effectiveness of the strategy.

2. Internal Communication

Internal communication within the Europe-LAND project will happen at two levels:

- a) Communication between the EU and Europe-LAND
- b) Communication amongst project partners

Communication between the EU and Europe-LAND will include regular reports, deliverables etc. via the EU portal, as well as regular email and/or exchange with the assigned EU project officer from EC-CINEA. The consortium will inform EC-CINEA before any communication activities which may be expected to generate a major digital impact so that the EU may further support outreach via own channels, and invitations to targeted events and project meetings will be send in advance.

Internal communication amongst the project partners is based on regular teleconferences, emails, the project internal Trello platform, a shared online repository, scheduled face-to-face project assemblies, other meetings and workshops. Communication within the project needs to be fluid and comprehensive in order to assure efficient and high-quality collaborative work. A meeting structure outlining the main scheduled meetings, dates and topics is included in D1.1 Project Handbook and the periodic updates D1.2, D1.3 and D1.4. Internal project communications will preferably be carried out via the following four channels:

1. **Trello:** For effective project management, full visibility over all relevant tasks and flexibility to rearrange them as project's priorities change are needed. Trello, an online project management tool, allows user to break up tasks into lists and cards, and manage their progress by moving these cards through the lists. This solves the problem of long email threads, wasted meetings, accountability, clarifying and explaining projects, forgetfulness and transparency. By having multiple boards and lists for all WPs, all partners can report, communicate and track progress of a specific task on one platform, without the need for email exchange or meetings. To ensure all partners are familiar with the tool to use its full potential, an online introduction course into the basic functionalities was offered to the project partners by the WP 7 lead on three separate dates within the first project months.
2. **HiDrive:** This is the common project document repository for the whole project. HiDrive allows for real time collaboration on documents, which reduces the need for versioning and makes sharing documents easier. Internally, the folders are structured by work packages and tasks, allowing for a better overview and quick access. For more information on data management and protection, please refer to D1.5 Data Management Plan (M6).
3. **Zoom:** This web-based conferencing tool allows to join web meetings remotely without the need for installing an app, making meetings and conferences faster and easier to hold. Zoom also offers a variety of additional tools, such as build-in polling tools, break-out rooms, collaboration tools and subtitles in multiple languages. Other conferencing tools may also be used, e.g. in case partners organize WP meeting as e-meetings and their institution provides only a different tool.
4. **Regular E-mail/Europe-LAND Mailing list:** An internal list of emails of all partners working on the project has been collected and sorted into 4 categories: lead PI, team member, finance, legal and administration. This division allows targeted outreach when dealing with different issues within the project. This communication list is used to announce urgent matters and to carry out communications and management activities. The list is continuously updated and maintained by the WP1 and WP7 leaders.

3. External Communication and Dissemination of Results

3.1 Objectives

Unsustainable land-use is one of the major drivers behind climate change and plays a key role in several other sustainability issues such as food security, biodiversity and the provision of renewable resources. As such, it is of crucial importance to effectively communicate the potential of sustainable land-use and land management for climate change mitigation and adaptation to a variety of stakeholders in order to drive the change towards a more sustainable system.

The Europe-LAND project is committed to not only openly and freely share all project results and the methodology applied but further to emphasize their value to the general public, policy makers and land-use stakeholders. A strategic planning of all external communication is necessary to maximize its effect and lead to the envisaged impact.

The specific objectives behind external communication within the project can be summarized in the following clusters:

1. **Visibility:** Making the project, its activities and results visible and known by a wide range of stakeholders and target audiences

2. Networking: Exchanging information and resources with expert stakeholders and other projects to build connections and form synergies for mutual input
3. Exploitation and Upscaling: Preparing project information, methodology and results to be implemented in new contexts and applied to scenarios outside the scope of the project.

3.2 Audiences

Based on the focus and the objectives of the Europe-LAND project, four main groups of target audiences have been identified and a detailed analysis of their preferred communication channels was carried out. The main target audiences and the results of the analysis are compiled in Table 1.

Table 1: Target Audience Groups and preferred communication channels

Target Audience Group	Target audience sub-groups	Preferred communication channels
Land-use stakeholders	e.g. land-users, land-owners, farmers, agriculture organizations, foresters, forestry organizations, landscape and national park authorities	Agricultural Fairs and exhibitions, podcast programs, Social media platforms such as Facebook and Twitter (X), website, workshops and webinars, local newspapers, email newsletters
Public authorities	e.g. local, regional and national authorities, regulatory agencies, policy makers, farm federations, citizen associations	Policy briefs and reports, workshops and webinars, stakeholder meetings, media outreach, Social media platforms such as LinkedIn and Twitter (X)
Scientific community	e.g. experts, researchers, NGOs, spatial planning engineers, science communicators	Academic publications, webinars, social media, email newsletters, scientific conferences and events, social media platforms such as LinkedIn and Twitter (X)
Extended target group	General public, consumers, media	Social media platforms such as Twitter (X) and LinkedIn, traditional media, newspapers, podcasts

By employing a mix of the identified communication channels and strategies, the Europe-LAND project aims to effectively reach its target audiences, foster meaningful engagement and ensure the project outcomes are widely disseminated and implemented for the benefit of all stakeholders.

3.3 Approach

Based on the identified communication channels used by the target audiences of the Europe-LAND project and the Grant Agreement, the project will employ a range of external communication tools and channels listed below in chapter 3.3.1 and 3.3.2 to maximize the reach and impact of the project. The following section lists the planned communication activities and online communication. This list will be updated and adjusted according to changing needs over the project duration, which will be reflected in the yearly updates of this CDUE-Plan (D7.2, D7.3, D7.4) in the scope of Task 7.1.

In order to ensure that all external communication of the project is coherent and recognizable, a project brand consisting of a logo, poster, flyer and templates for public presentations as well as deliverables was created and shared with the consortium partners to be used for dissemination activities. The project brand can be found on the shared project HiDrive: **WP7-> T7.2 Project branding, communication material and digital outreach.**

3.3.1 Main Activities

In an effort to achieve the communication objectives of the Europe-LAND project, a wide range of dissemination and communication activities are planned over the course of the project. They are laid out in more detail in the following section and comprise promotional material, a project video, regular project newsletters, oral and virtual presentations, technical workshops and capacity-building seminars, webinars, open access publications, podcasts and press releases. The activities planned in this section are subject to the continuous reporting within T7.4 and will be included in D7.7 and D7.8.

Project poster and leaflet

As part of the recognizable project brand, a project poster and leaflet were developed and shared with partners for open use in their facilities and at events, workshops and conferences. The standard language of the dissemination material is English. For the project leaflet, a template was created, for partners to customize with their own contact information and for translation into local languages, if needed.

Figure 1: Europe-LAND Project Poster

Project video

A video detailing the projects scope and objectives will be developed by M12 to be used for further dissemination and to be displayed on the project website and social media.

Regular Newsletters

5 periodic newsletters will be published every 6 months starting in M18. It will be made available for download on the project website and will be distributed and advertised over the project’s social media accounts. Topics will be decided by WP7 leaders and articles and contributions created in collaboration with the project partners and potential external experts and stakeholders.

Presentations at conferences and events

Consortium partners over the course of the project duration will attend a variety of events and conferences at which they will represent the project, present project results and advertise project outcomes. To ensure a coherent public presence of the project, templates for presentations and dissemination materials such as posters and flyers are provided within the project brand to be used at these public appearances.

Furthermore, presentations and attendances at events and conferences as part of the project dissemination are subject to the continuous reporting to the project coordinator and the EU. An internal reporting system is set-up to allow for easy reporting of such activities, which will feed into the deliverables D7.7 and D7.8 in T7.4 and will periodically be updated in the EU portal.

Technical workshops and seminars

One key element to exploit project results are technical workshops and seminars that will be organized by WP7 leaders in collaboration with various consortium partners to reach a wide range of audiences. The list of already planned technical workshops may be extended over the course of the project, when further subjects of interest or relevant target audiences are identified by project partners.

Table 2: Technical workshops already planned.

Short description	When	Who	Target audience
Revealing land-use behaviour and its drivers in Europe	M12	HAW & UCPH	Researchers and land users, which can be local farmers, agribusinesses or public authorities.
Towards a better understanding of land-use decisions related to climate change and biodiversity	M18	HAW & IGAR	Land users, managers, local authorities, regulatory agencies.
Prospective trends in the mapping of future expected land use and land cover patterns	M24	HAW & UL	Local authorities, regulatory agencies, decision-makers.
New economic and behavioural tools in support of mitigation and adaptation	M36	HAW & SUA	Land users, decision-makers, regulatory agencies.
Introducing the Europe-LAND toolbox	M45	HAW & AUTH	Policy makers, local authorities, regulatory agencies, farm federations and agriculture organizations, spatial planning engineers, NGOs, citizen associations, researchers and anyone interested in the topic.

Webinars

Within the first year of the project, 6 expert webinars will be organized by WP7 in cooperation with other WP leaders to reflect on insights from stakeholders and their key motivations behind land-use decisions in order to gain an understanding of the awareness of climate change and biodiversity challenges within the stakeholder group. A more detailed planning for the webinar series will be included in D7.6 Stakeholder Engagement Strategy, scheduled for M6.

Open Access Scientific Publications and Reports

Europe-LAND project results will be arranged to develop peer-reviewed articles, book chapters and reports intended for scientific audiences. These scientific outputs will cover theoretical issues, conceptual and methodological questions and key results. In addition, research data will be made

available as much as possible. All scientific publications will be open access whenever possible. Publications will be immediately uploaded to OpenAIRE and the project website to maximize the reach.

Podcasts

A public dedicated podcast series titled “European Land Use Talks” will be launched in M6, featuring key project outputs as well as complementary research and insights into land-use and sustainability issues in Europe. The episodes will be recorded and produced by WP7 leaders and host a series of guests from a variety of different expert and target stakeholder groups. The podcast series will allow to attract an audience that prefers to listening to project results rather than reading newsletters or reports.

Press releases

In order to enhance visibility of the Europe-LAND project and to inform all target audiences about the project, traditional media will be supplied with one press release per year. The main media companies in the partner countries relevant to the project are listed in table 3. Besides, PR offices of partner organizations might further support dissemination of press releases over their networks.

Table 3: Media companies in the partner countries relevant to the project

Country	Media companies
Austria	Krone Zeitung Der Standard
Czech Republic	Dnes Deník Hospořáské noviny
Denmark	Politiken Weekendavisen Altinget.dk Jyllands Posten Berlingske Tidende
Estonia	Daily: Postimees; Eesti Päevaleht; Ohtuleht Weekly: Eest Ekspress; Maaleht
Germany	Die Zeit FAZ Der Spiegel Süddeutsche Zeitung TAZ
Greece	Efimerida ron Syntakton To Vima Kathimerini
Italy	Corriere della Sera La Repubblica
Latvia	Latvijas Avīze Neatkarīgā Rīta Avīze
Portugal	Público Expresso Jornal de Notícias Observador
Poland	Gazeta Wyborcza Fakt Rzeczypospolita

	Portal Onet
Romania	Adevărul Libertatea
Slovakia	Pravda Hospodárske noviny Roľnícke noviny

In addition to this CDUE-Plan D7.1 and its subsequent updates (D7.2, D7.3, D7.4), a dedicated Stakeholder Engagement Strategy (D7.6) will be developed by M6, detailing a planning for all participatory actions involving stakeholders within the project. The following points may be included in D7.6: a) an expert webinar series, b) regular expert exchanges, c) yearly strategic exchanges with EU representatives and related EU projects, d) continuous collaboration with relevant research projects, and e) a final conference reaching at least 100 stakeholders at the end of the project.

3.3.2 Online Communication

In addition to the planned activities to disseminate and communicate project outputs, a broad online presence will be established for the Europe-LAND project. Online communication will be established in form of a dedicated project website and social media accounts on LinkedIn and tentatively X (formerly Twitter), which will be launched by M7, pertaining to Milestone 4. Planned activities for the website and social media accounts are laid out in the following section.

Website

Serving as a home base for all communications, the website (www.europe.land.eu) will be a key channel to communicate project activities to all target audience groups. The main language of the website will be English, but sections in local languages of the partners will be added where appropriate to engage more potential stakeholders.

The website will include one section with general project information, such as objectives, technological implications, methodology and links to related sites. Partner information will also be included, linking to the respective partner’s official website. Another section will be included which will be regularly updated with project activities, news and announcements of upcoming events and other information which might be of interest to the scientific community, consumers and land-users. An internal list to track the news posts on the website recording the title, topic, responsible person, scheduled posting time and actual posting time will be made available on the project shared file system on HiDrive. A third section will include links to relevant resources and information on the datasets as well as tools developed within the project’s scope. Public material, such as public deliverables, scientific publications and newsletters will be available for download.

The website will be maintained for at least 5 years after the project duration ends, to ensure maximum exploitation.

Tools and resources developed within the project scope, such as the toolbox developed in WP6, will be hosted on partners’ local websites to facilitate the set-up and will be linked to the resources section on the project website. A future implementation of the tools into the project website directly will be discussed further during the project duration.

Project partner websites

In order to maximize the reach of the project communication, each partner may use their organization's website to share important outputs of the project. Table xx compiles all partner websites.

Table 4: Project partner websites

Partner	website URL
HAW	https://www.haw-hamburg.de/en/ftz-nk/
AUTH	https://www.auth.gr/en/
EMU	https://pk.emu.ee/en/structure/environmentalprotectionandlandscapemanagement/
UCPH	https://ign.ku.dk/english/research/geography/environment-society-developing-countries/
UC	Centre for Functional Ecology: https://cfe.uc.pt/ Department of Life Sciences: https://www.uc.pt/ctuc/dcv/ University of Coimbra: https://www.uc.pt/
UNIBO	https://scienzeaziendali.unibo.it/en/index.html
IGAR	http://geoinst.ro/index.html
BUT	Main page: https://pb.edu.pl/en/ Faculty of Engineering Management: https://wiz.pb.edu.pl/en/ Faculty of Civil Engineering and Environmental Sciences: https://wb.pb.edu.pl/en/
LU	https://www.lu.lv/en/
SUA	Main page: https://www.uniag.sk/en/main-page Faculty of Economics and Management: https://fem.uniag.sk/en/home/
BOKU	https://boku.ac.at/en/wiso/sec
IAMO	https://lsg.iamo.de/
CU	https://www.natur.cuni.cz/eng https://www.tilspec.cz/

Social Media

To maximize the public reach and awareness of project results, the project will be extensively promoted on social media channels. Based on the target audience analysis presented in section 3.2, all target groups can be reached by establishing presences on LinkedIn and Twitter. Multimedia content like pictures, infographics and videos generated from project reports, events and partner activities will be posted to relevant groups and pages, to invite public exchange about the project and its implications for land-use practices, policy and research. All facts and figures will be referenced to the corresponding website page to lead interested parties to the relevant contact persons.

All posts will be planned and scheduled in advance to ensure regular activity on all channels. A detailed social media planning containing information on each post, a responsible person, a scheduled posting time and actual posting time is available on HiDrive: **WP7 -> T7.2 Europe-LAND project branding, communication material and digital outreach -> Social Media**.

LinkedIn and Twitter will be employed to establish a mass online networking community, the Community of Practice to build synergies. A detailed plan will be developed in scope of D7.5 Action-Plan for Community of Practice due in M9.

To maximize the reach on social media and make sure to reach intended audiences and interested parties, appropriate hashtags will be used for each post. As a base for all posts the hashtags #Landuse; #Sustainability; #Agriculture and #CINEA were identified. For specific posts regarding Webinars or findings, workshops, policy relevant information etc. the posts will indicate these activities and topics with corresponding hashtags (e.g. #Workshop; #Webinar; #Policy).

LinkedIn

A LinkedIn company page was set up for the Europe-LAND project. It is available here: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/europe-land/>. The page is managed by HAW as WP7 lead with the aim to share weekly updates on the project activities and results, events as well as relevant information on land-use in Europe in general. LinkedIn is an ideal platform to connect with experts and professional stakeholders and foster a network for potential synergies. At the time of submission of this deliverable, the LinkedIn page of Europe-LAND had 65 followers.

Figure 2: The Europe-LAND LinkedIn page

X

An X (formerly Twitter) account for the project is planned to be set-up to post regular short updates on the project activities and to engage in current discussions on land-use and sustainability issues. The page will be managed by HAW as the lead of WP7.

In the past, X has been an effective tool to reach policymakers, the scientific community as well as the general public. Under current developments, e.g. the undergoing re-branding of the platform, many scientific members are leaving the platform, making it necessary to reevaluate if the tool will still be a suitable choice for project communication.

As the future of X as an effective communication platform remains uncertain, the situation will be re-evaluated by WP7 leaders in 12 months to make a decision on whether the Europe-LAND project will continue to use X for online dissemination or if a switch to a different platform might be necessary. The future updates of the CDUE-Plan (D7.2, D7.3, D7.4) will be changed accordingly.

Besides the dedicated LinkedIn and X accounts for the project, which will be maintained by HAW and be updated in English, project partners might employ their own institutions’ social media accounts on different platforms to post about the most important updates or advertise local events. The local accounts might be useful to reach local stakeholders who are not using the main social media platforms or are communicating in local languages. A list of partners’ social media accounts is compiled in table 5.

Table 5: Project partners’ social media accounts

Partner	Social Media handle
HAW	LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/research-and-transfer-center-sustainable-development-and-climate-change-management
AUTh	Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/auth_university_thessaloniki/ Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/Aristoteleio/ LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/aristotle-university-of-thessaloniki-auth/?originalSubdomain=gr Twitter: https://twitter.com/Aristoteleio
EMU	Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/EMUkeskkonnakaitse
UCPH	LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/school/university-of-copenhagen/
UC	Centre for Functional Ecology Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/CFEUC Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/cfe_uc/ LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/centre-for-functional-ecology-science-for-people-the-planet/ Twitter: https://twitter.com/CFE_UC YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/@CentreforFunctionalEcology Department of Life Sciences Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/fctucDCV Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/dcv_uc/ Twitter: https://twitter.com/DCV_UC YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/@departamentodecienciasdavi8940/featured University of Coimbra Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/univdecoimbra Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/ucoimbra/ Twitter: https://twitter.com/univdecoimbra YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCwJWYs4uKz77qR_NaruUcBg LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/school/universidade-de-coimbra/
UNIBO	LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/disa-universit%C3%A0-di-bologna/?originalSubdomain=it YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLaUmBQ7P5K-C9D_vHNFLK-Vk8-5eQMcf

BUT	LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/school/politechnika-bia%C5%82ostocka/?originalSubdomain=pl
LU	LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/university-of-latvia/ Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/universitate/ Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/latvijasuniversitate/ Twitter: https://twitter.com/universitateLV
SUA	Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/SPUNitra/ Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/spunitra/
BOKU	Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/socialecologyvienna/ Twitter: https://twitter.com/BOKU_SEC
IAMO	Twitter: https://twitter.com/iamoLSG
CU	Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/kagik.cuni https://www.facebook.com/prf.uk.praha Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/kagik.cuni/?hl=cs https://www.instagram.com/natur_cuni/?hl=cs

4. Exploitation and Upscaling

With the measures and activities laid out so far, Europe-LAND will ensure a wide visibility and networking of the project. However, the project also strives to go beyond the communication and dissemination of project activities and outputs to widen the project’s impact: It delivers knowledge, tools and methodologies that can be further developed and reused, i.e. exploited by others. A dedicated Exploitation Strategy for the project results will be developed within Task 6.5 and will be detailed in deliverable D6.5 Exploitation Plan due in M46, drawing out a detailed planning on establishing and exploiting project results beyond the scope and duration of the project. In the frame of this deliverable D7.1 and its subsequent updates, a more general plan for the exploitation and upscaling of project results over the whole course of the project will be drawn out.

The project partners defined some priorities for the exploitation of results in the Grant Agreement:

- “To foster and encourage the deployment of innovative tools;
- to create a virtuous and sustainable loop between research and innovation;
- to ensure the strong commitment of the project stakeholders, from policy-makers to citizens;
- to widely spread the knowledge on the demonstrated tools generated by the project, so that as many organizations as possible may benefit from them.”

To achieve these goals, Europe-LAND will employ various measures. All methodology, as far as possible, will be made freely available and replicability will be a main concern, which all partners will work towards. Furthermore, capacity building programmes such as workshops, webinars, a MOOC and a summer school, as well as the toolbox and various stakeholder collaborations will aid in making project results available and applicable for stakeholders to act as multipliers, and to adapt project results to new contexts and areas. The Europe-LAND Community of Practice (CoP), established online, will foster networking and discussions on the methodology and outputs and create direct feedback loops with external experts, relevant EU projects and policymakers. It will serve as a long-lasting platform on current and future land-use and land management issues across Europe, beyond the project duration, sustained by the Coordinator.

Over the course of the project, further exploitation and upscaling goals and activities will be planned and implemented, extending on this CDUE-Plan in future versions.

5. Partner responsibilities

HAW Hamburg is the lead of WP7 and therefore the main responsibility of managing, monitoring and reporting regarding communication and dissemination as well as upscaling and exploitation lies with the HAW. Nevertheless, all partners play a crucial role in achieving dissemination goals and are therefore involved in the activities of WP7. Partners have received funding for various activities such as open access publications and attendance to conferences, hosting project events and preparing dissemination materials. Some partners also hold special responsibility for co-hosting webinars, events, the MOOC and summer school. In addition, all partners might be asked by WP7 leads to contribute information, pictures or short texts on their respective expertise and work within the project for use on social media or the website or to contribute to one of the newsletters. During the project preparation, all partners were asked to allocate some staff efforts to WP7 for this purpose.

In order to ensure a coherent and recognizable project brand, all partners are strongly encouraged to use the provided templates for dissemination activities, which can be found in the project brand package on HiDrive: **WP7-> T7.2 Project branding, communication material and digital outreach.**

During all dissemination activities, partners are responsible for accurately acknowledging EU-funding according to the agreed-upon terms in the Grant Agreement, in order to be eligible for funding of said communication activities.

All partners are furthermore responsible for reporting all dissemination and communication activities to WP7 leads within one week, or for open access publications immediately, to be included in the continuous project reporting internally as well as towards the EU.

6. Monitoring and evaluation of CDUE activities

In order to ensure a high-quality execution of the communication strategy, continuous monitoring and evaluation is of high importance. The Europe-LAND project will establish an overall monitoring and evaluation framework in scope of T1.4 and D1.8 due in M6. However, a separate monitoring focused on CDUE activities is vital to ensure that the project will achieve the intended impact.

In course of the project, WP7 will produce deliverables comprising reports and records of the wide range of planned dissemination and communication activities. D7.7 (M24) and D7.8 (M48) will comprise extensive reports on all dissemination activities and online communication laid out in this CDUE-Plan and its yearly updates that will have taken place during the respective reporting periods (M1 to M24 and M25 to M48). This information will also be continuously updated on the EU portal by the WP7 leader. Additionally, D6.6 (M45) will give a summary of the technical capacity building seminars carried out over the course of the project.

Besides tracking the dissemination and communication activities themselves with the internally set-up trackings for events attended, publications, social media and website posts and following the schedule for webinars, workshops, events, podcasts, etc. and the deliverables mentioned above, the project also aims to measure how effective these communication actions are and to quantify the impact of them.

In order to do so, some key performance indicators (KPIs) were defined in the Grant Agreement and will be monitored over the course of the project. The KPIs defined are listed the table 6 (see next page).

Each year, the progression on the KPIs will be measured and recorded to allow a direct comparison with the set goals.

Table 6: Key performance indicators for the impact of communication and dissemination activities

Key performance indicators	Poor impact	Good impact	Excellent impact
Material downloads from website	<100	100-200	>200
Relevant contacts made through website	<15	15-30	>30
Number of followers on social media	<500	500-1000	>1000
Number of interactions (e.g. likes, comments, shares)	<800	800-1200	>1200
Number of papers submitted	<10	10-15	>15
Number of publications downloaded on website	<30	30-50	>50
Number of brochures distributed	<300	300-500	>500
Number of video views	<500	500-1000	>1000
Number of newsletter subscribers	<500	500-1000	>1000
Number of cooperations with projects and initiatives	<5	5-15	>15
Number of events organized	<6	6-10	>10
Number of external events attended	<6	6-10	>10
Number of total people reached through events by the end of the project	<100	100-500	>500
Members in community of practice	<1000	1000-1500	>1500
Number of followers of podcast series	<500	500-1000	>1000
Number of webinars held	<3	3-5	>5
Number of participants/webinar	<50	50-150	>150
Number of workshops held	<3	3-5	>5
Number of participants/workshop	<10	10-30	>30
Number of participants of final conference	<50	50-100	>100